

Effect of liming on the changes of different forms of potassium in an acid soil treated with N and K fertilizers

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Abstract : A laboratory experiment was conducted to study the effect of liming on the transformation of different forms of potassium in a strongly acidic silty loam soil (pH 4.56) treated with nitrogenous and potassic fertilizers. Irrespective of treatments, liming initially decreased the water soluble and exchangeable K but increased the non-exchangeable K in soil. Water soluble K was significantly increased in limed soil throughout its incubation period, whereas it showed a decreasing trend in unlimed acid soil. Highest amount of exchangeable K was observed in acid soil after 90 days of incubation, whereas water soluble and non-exchangeable K were found to be highest in half and full limed soil respectively. Combined application of nitrogen and potassium fertilizer significantly increased the water soluble K. However exchangeable K was increased in sole potassium fertilizer treated system. Application of N along with K fertilizer influenced soil K fixation and release of K because of its antagonistic interaction between NH_4^+ and K^+ for the same fixing sites.

Keywords : Acid soil, exchangeable K, liming, nitrogen and potassium fertilizer, non-exchangeable K, water soluble K.

Introduction

Potassium (K) is one of the most essential macronutrient for plant, which with nitrogen and phosphorus plays an important role in plant growth and development. Nitrogen is commonly known to be most yield increasing plant nutrient and K is most important in stabilizing the yield. The importance of K in Indian agriculture has increased with intensification of agriculture. Compared to N, application of K has been neglected in many developing countries and this has resulted in the continual depletion of K from soils^{1,2}. Availability of K to plants depends upon the forms of K present in soil are of solution, exchangeable, non-exchangeable and mineral origin³. Water soluble K, which is taken up directly by plants⁴; exchangeable K, held by negatively charged sites of clay particles and non-exchangeable K are trapped between layers of expanding lattice clays⁵. There is very less amount of K is present in soil solution (0.1–0.2%) and available (1–2%) forms as compared to non-exchangeable form (1–10%)⁶. Availability of K to plant is controlled by dynamic interactions among its different chemical forms⁷. The equilibrium between soluble K and exchangeable K is fast and is established within few min-

utes, but that between the exchangeable K and non-exchangeable K is much slower, requiring few days to even few weeks to establish⁸. Within one rotation cycle, exchangeable K and water soluble K are the main forms of potassium available to the plant, and little non-exchangeable K could be absorbed⁹.

All these forms of K in soil are affected by liming. However, the actual relationship between liming and potassium availability is not clear yet. Within the forms of K water soluble K increased but exchangeable K decreased in all the soils after liming¹⁰. Liming has positive influence in exchangeable and reserved form of K¹¹. Liming may disturb the K balance in soil by increasing pH which leads to increase microbial activity in acid soil. Liming generally increase K fixation in soil, though liming soils of acidic reaction increased the cumulative release of potassium over unlimed system¹². Optimal N and K application is very important to best nutrient management in agriculture. A nitrogen-potassium interaction generally exists in agricultural ecosystems¹³. Application of nitrogenous and potassic fertilizers significantly affect water soluble and exchangeable forms of K in soil¹⁴, that means N-K interaction also affects the soil K fixation and

release. Keeping above information in view, the present study was undertaken to investigate the effect of liming on changes different forms of K treated with different doses of N and K fertilizers.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

(a) Electrical balance : Model No. PB 602-S (MonoBloc inside), (b) Digital pH meter : Model No. 802 (Systronics), (c) Flamephotometer : Model No. FP 102 (Chemito Technologies Pvt. Ltd.), (d) Mechanical rotary shaker (MULTISPAN) and (e) Electrical hot plate.

Materials :

(a) Soil : The soil sample (0–15 cm depth) used in the present investigation was collected from Anandapur Tea State (26°78'N and 88°39'E), Malbazar, Jalpaiguri (West Bengal) during the year 2010-11, (b) Water : Double-distilled water was used for analytical purpose, (c) Fertilizers : Urea (46% N), SSP (16% P₂O₅), MOP (60% K₂O) from Tata Chemicals Ltd., (d) Liming materials : 100% pure CaCO₃ by Merck Ltd. and (e) Filter paper : Whatman No. 1 filter paper.

Reagents (Merck Ltd.) :

(a) Neutral normal ammonium acetate (NH₄OAc) and (b) 1 N nitric acid (HNO₃).

Soil sample preparation, liming and soil analysis :

The soil was air dried, powdered, passed through a 2 mm nylon sieve and considered as unlimed soil in experiment. Lime requirement of that acid soil was determined by Shoemaker, McLean and Pratt method in short SMP buffer method¹⁵. Based on the lime requirement (30 tons ha⁻¹) half limed soil and full limed soil were prepared by uniform mixing of the liming materials (CaCO₃), equivalent to half dose (at 15 tons ha⁻¹) and full dose (at 30 tons ha⁻¹) of lime requirement respectively. Liming was done in two separate plastic containers, containing 1 kg of soil each and allowed the liming material to react with soil mass for 3 months with repeated wetting up to its water holding capacity, followed by air drying to prepare half limed and full lime soil. Before use, both the half and full limed soils were air dried, ground by and passed through 2 mm sieve. Altogether six sets of treatments were adopted for three sets of both limed and unlimed soils. For every treatment 10 g of both half limed and full limed as well as

unlimed acid soil were taken separately in 100 mL beakers for the incubation study. First set was maintained as control without addition of nitrogen and potassium fertilizers. In the second set, K was added as treatment material at 30 mg kg⁻¹ in the form of Muriate of Potash (MOP). In the third set N was added at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as urea. The fourth set was maintained with both K and N addition at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as MOP and urea respectively. In the fifth set, nitrogen was added at 60 mg kg⁻¹ as urea. The sixth set of soil was maintained where, K (as MOP) and N (as urea) were added at 30 mg kg⁻¹ and 60 mg kg⁻¹ respectively. Application of all these fertilizers were done by dissolving those in distilled water at their respected doses and the soil samples were moistened to 60% of the moisture holding capacity. After moistening, the soil samples were allowed to incubate at room temperature (30 ± 20 °C) for period of 90 days.

Five separate sets were maintained for laboratory analysis on 0th, 15th, 30th, 60th and 90th day of incubation. Soil samples for all sets along with three replications were identically collected for analysis of water soluble K [in 1 : 5 soil-water suspension¹⁶], exchangeable K [deducting water soluble K from neutral normal NH₄OAc (1 : 5) extractable K¹⁷], non-exchangeable K [deducting neutral normal NH₄OAc (1 : 5) extractable K from boiling 1 N HNO₃ (1 : 10) extractable K¹⁸]. All the forms of extractable K were determined by flame photometer. Loss of moisture due to evaporation was replenished by the addition of distilled water on every alternate day by difference in weight. The treatments adopted in incubation study for each unlimed (L₀), half limed (L_{1/2}) and full limed (L₁) soil are represented as follows.

T₀ = Soil, T₁ = Soil + K at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as MOP, T₂ = Soil + N at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as urea, T₃ = Soil + K at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as MOP + N at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as urea, T₄ = Soil + N at 60 mg kg⁻¹ as urea, T₅ = Soil + K at 30 mg kg⁻¹ as MOP + N at 60 mg kg⁻¹ as urea.

All the data were statistically analyzed following methods meant for completely randomized design (CRD). Their mean effects were further subjected to Post-Hoc test to identify homogeneous means at 5% level of significance.

Results and discussion

Water soluble K :

The amount of water soluble K was significantly in-

creased throughout its incubation study in unlimed and both the limed soils with addition of K fertilizer (Table 1). Water soluble K was increased due to the addition of K fertilizer¹¹. The addition of N fertilizer in both

in water soluble K due to liming owes its origin to K fixation by precipitating Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} and freeing the blocked negatively charged sites of soil which leads to the conversion of water soluble K into exchangeable form.

Table 1. Changes in the amount of water soluble K ($mg\ kg^{-1}$) in an acid soil and its corresponding limed soil treated with or without inorganic N and K fertilizers either alone or in combinations

Periods	Lime level (L)	Treatments (T)						Mean	CD (0.05)	
		T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅			
0th day	L ₀	30.00	49.83	30.33	50.50	30.17	50.33	40.19	T	1.24
	L _{1/2}	12.00	15.00	13.00	14.00	14.00	15.00	13.83	L	0.88
	L ₁	10.00	12.00	11.00	13.00	12.00	14.00	12.00	T X L	2.15
	Mean	17.33	25.61	18.11	25.83	18.72	26.44			
15th day	L ₀	24.67	44.00	26.00	44.17	27.50	45.50	35.31	T	0.76
	L _{1/2}	14.00	18.00	16.00	17.00	17.00	19.00	16.83	L	0.54
	L ₁	8.00	10.00	10.00	12.00	10.00	13.00	10.50	T X L	1.31
	Mean	15.56	24.00	17.33	24.39	18.17	25.83			
30th day	L ₀	21.50	34.00	23.50	37.00	25.50	40.00	30.25	T	0.68
	L _{1/2}	19.00	21.17	22.00	24.00	25.00	27.00	23.03	L	0.48
	L ₁	11.00	12.00	14.00	16.00	16.00	18.00	14.50	T X L	1.18
	Mean	17.17	22.39	19.83	25.67	22.17	28.33			
60th day	L ₀	18.33	29.00	20.50	32.00	22.00	35.50	26.22	T	0.72
	L _{1/2}	23.67	30.00	27.00	33.00	29.50	36.00	29.86	L	0.51
	L ₁	12.00	14.00	15.00	17.50	17.00	21.00	16.08	T X L	1.25
	Mean	18.00	24.33	20.83	27.50	22.83	30.83			
90th day	L ₀	15.67	25.50	18.00	28.00	20.00	31.00	23.03	T	0.75
	L _{1/2}	30.00	38.00	32.00	40.00	33.50	42.00	35.92	L	0.53
	L ₁	14.00	15.67	16.00	17.00	17.00	20.00	16.61	T X L	1.31
	Mean	19.89	26.39	22.00	28.33	23.50	31.00			

[Where, L₀, L_{1/2}, L₁ indicate unlimed, half limed soil, full limed soil respectively, T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅ indicate no fertilizer, K @ 30 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as MOP, N @ 30 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as urea, K @ 30 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as MOP and N @ 30 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as urea, N @ 60 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as urea, K @ 30 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ MOP and N @ 60 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ as urea respectively, NS = not significant].

lower and higher doses with K fertilizer increased the water soluble K in all soils compared to addition of K fertilizer alone. This is attributed to the fact that soils have only limited number of fixation sites and the NH_4^+ ion, released from N fertilizer compete with water soluble K^+ and hence reduce K fixation and increased the amount of water soluble K in soils¹⁹. However, sole addition of nitrogenous fertilizer did not show any significant effect on increase in water soluble K in soils.

Effect of liming on water soluble K :

Irrespective of treatments, water soluble K was significantly affected by liming (Fig. 1). Initially on (0th day) water soluble K was decreased significantly in both the limed soils than that of unlimed system. The decrease

Mass action of Ca^{2+} ions which are added to soils through liming is also responsible for the decrease of water soluble K in acid soil. Therefore water soluble K is negatively correlated with $CaCO_3$ content in soil²⁰. Results (Fig. 1) further revealed that water soluble K showed a decreasing trend in unlimed but an increasing trend in both the limed soils with the period of investigation. The presence of Ca^{2+} replaces exchangeable K from its exchange phase and as a result of which water soluble K is increased in the soil²¹. The increase in water soluble K over time is more prominent in half limed than full limed soil. Thus it is clear from the results that addition of lime to half of soil's requirement is sufficient to maintain the water soluble K in larger amount. Increase in water soluble K over 90

Fig. 1. Effect of liming on the changes of the mean value of different treatments on water soluble K.

day is comparatively less in full limed soil than that of half limed soil. The amount of Ca^{2+} applied through half limed soil is sufficient to displace the K from the exchange complex to solution phase and excess amount of Ca^{2+} through full limed soil is unable to displace the exchangeable K in solution form. This is perhaps due to short period of incubation of limed soil under study.

Exchangeable K :

Comparatively higher amount of exchangeable K was accumulated in soil treated with K fertilizer alone (Table 2). The decrease in water soluble K with concomitant increase in exchangeable K pointed out that these two forms of K are present in equilibrium⁸. Comparatively lesser amount of exchangeable K was accumulated in soils where K fertilizer was added along with N ferti-

lizer. This is due to the presence of NH_4^+ ions which hinders the occupation of exchange phase only by K^+ ions. Addition of either doses of N did not show any significant variation in accumulation of exchangeable K in soils. This trend of results was observed throughout the period of investigation due to mass action of higher amount of N^{22} .

Effect of liming on exchangeable K :

Irrespective of treatments, addition of liming decreased the exchangeable K in soil system (Fig. 2). Precipitation of exchangeable aluminium (Al^{3+}) and iron (Fe^{3+}) ions as hydroxy-aluminium and hydroxy-iron polymers which act as props between layer silicates, thereby inhibiting the collapse of the layers for the K ions. The latter enhances K selectivity²³. The decrease in exchangeable K on liming may also be associated with a drastic reduction of H_3O^+ ions²⁴. The amount of exchangeable K is more in full limed as compared to half limed soil. This is due to liming with higher doses; higher amount of Ca^{2+} occupy the exchange sites which encourages release of non-exchangeable K in the exchangeable phase. In acid soil and half limed soil, irrespective of treatments, the amount of exchangeable K increased up to 60th day and then showed a slight decrease in the amount on 90th day of the experiment (Fig. 2). However, the amount of decrease in exchangeable K^+ from 60th to 90th day is more marked in half limed than that of unlimed soil due to presence of Ca^{2+} in the system. This slight decrease in the amount of

Table 2. Changes in the amount of exchangeable K (mg kg^{-1}) in an acid soil and its corresponding limed soil treated with or without inorganic N and K fertilizers either alone or in combinations

Periods	Lime level (L)	Treatments (T)						Mean	CD (0.05)	
		T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅			
0th day	L ₀	132.33	140.67	130.67	139.67	129.33	139.67	132.33	T	5.57
	L _{1/2}	97.17	121.17	96.33	122.50	94.00	123.17	97.17	L	3.93
	L ₁	122.45	144.08	120.92	140.93	121.15	138.97	122.45	T X L	NS
	Mean	117.32	135.31	115.97	134.37	114.83	133.94			
15th day	L ₀	144.17	151.83	139.00	150.33	138.17	147.17	144.17	T	1.27
	L _{1/2}	104.17	125.17	99.83	126.17	98.33	125.33	104.17	L	0.90
	L ₁	137.17	154.17	133.17	147.92	130.83	142.17	137.17	T X L	2.21
	Mean	128.50	143.72	124.00	141.47	122.44	138.22			
30th day	L ₀	158.83	171.33	153.83	166.00	147.17	161.17	158.83	T	2.78
	L _{1/2}	115.67	139.33	111.83	134.33	107.33	128.33	115.67	L	1.96
	L ₁	149.93	161.33	142.17	154.33	137.50	148.83	149.93	T X L	4.81
	Mean	141.48	157.33	135.94	151.55	130.67	146.11			

Table-2 (contd.)

60th day	L ₀	180.67	191.00	175.67	186.17	168.33	179.17	180.67	T	1.63
	L _{1/2}	124.83	146.92	121.83	141.17	118.67	125.50	124.83	L	1.15
	L ₁	139.83	153.17	134.00	142.33	127.67	136.00	139.83	T X L	2.82
	Mean	148.44	163.70	143.83	156.56	138.22	146.89			
90th day	L ₀	174.50	187.33	171.32	183.83	167.17	177.83	174.50	T	0.86
	L _{1/2}	107.67	121.17	106.33	116.17	103.17	119.33	107.67	L	0.61
	L ₁	146.13	161.77	141.10	153.83	138.17	146.83	146.13	T X L	1.49
	Mean	142.77	156.76	139.58	151.28	136.17	148.00			

[Where, L₀, L_{1/2}, L₁ indicate unlimed, half limed soil, full limed soil respectively, T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅ indicate no fertilizer, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ as MOP, N @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ as urea, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ as MOP and N @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ as urea, N @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ as urea, K @ 30 mg kg⁻¹ MOP and N @ 60 mg kg⁻¹ as urea respectively, NS = not significant]

Fig. 2. Effect of liming on the changes of the mean value of different treatments on exchangeable K.

exchangeable K in the last stage of incubation is due to conversion of K⁺ ions from its exchangeable to non-exchangeable forms. Comparatively higher amount of exchangeable K⁺ was accumulated in full than that of half limed soil. Exchangeable K⁺ increased up to 30th day, then decreased on 60th and again increased on 90th day of the experiment in full limed soil. It also be noted here that changes in amount of exchangeable K is more prominent in unlimed as compared to limed system.

Non-exchangeable K :

Irrespective of treatments non-exchangeable K increased with increase in the period of incubation up to 60th day then decreased in all soils (Table 3). However, little change was recorded in unlimed soil. Highest amount of non-exchangeable K was recorded where K fertilizer was added alone. Presence of K in exchange phase is the prerequisite for its fixation. Saturation of the exchangeable complex with respect to K leads to entry of K into wedge zone and interlayer place. This leads to fixation of exchangeable K ions into non-exchangeable form²⁵. Higher dose of inorganic N along with K fertilizer renders

comparatively lesser amount of accumulation of non-exchangeable K over that of lower dose of N fertilizer in all soils. This is due to the competition of both NH₄⁺ and K⁺ for the same fixing sites in the clay minerals because NH₄⁺ and K⁺ have similar charges and hydrated diameters and the mechanism of fixation is same for both of these ions^{26,27}. Results (Table 3) further revealed that non-exchangeable K decreased up to 60th day in half limed and thereafter increased. However, and in full limed soil, amount of non-exchangeable K decreased during initial period of incubation up to 30th day, and then increased on 60th day, thereafter again decreased. These changes of non-exchangeable form of K were corroborated with the changes in exchangeable K content in both the soils and thus indicated the existence of dynamic equilibrium among these forms and shift of equilibrium from exchangeable to non-exchangeable form with time⁸.

Effect of liming on non-exchangeable K :

Liming increased non-exchangeable K in soils due to the precipitation of hydroxyl aluminium and hydroxyl iron polymers which block the release of non-exchangeable K (Fig. 3). The another reason for increase is that liming cause the expansion and weathering of lattice of clay minerals in soils which facilitate the release of lattice K. It is also clear from the data that not only liming but also its doses significantly affect the non-exchangeable K content in soils. For this reason, comparatively higher amount of non-exchangeable K is accumulated in full limed compared to that of half limed soil. This trend of result is observed irrespective of treatments and stages of incubation¹⁰.

Liming initially decreased water soluble K but increased the exchangeable K in soil. These exchangeable forms of K released as water soluble form afterwards. A part of

Table 3. Changes in the amount of non-exchangeable K (mg kg^{-1}) in an acid soil and its corresponding limed soil treated with or without inorganic N and K fertilizers either alone or in combinations

Periods	Lime level (L)	Treatments (T)					Mean	CD (0.05)		
		T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄				T ₅
0th day	L ₀	1658.00	1659.83	1657.09	1658.00	1657.23	1657.83	1658.00	T	NS
	L _{1/2}	2132.33	2132.00	2132.33	2130.80	2132.50	2130.13	2131.68	L	2.50
	L ₁	2267.50	2272.00	2267.37	2272.40	2267.00	2272.07	2269.72	T X L	NS
	Mean	2019.28	2021.28	2018.93	2020.40	2018.91	2020.01			
15th day	L ₀	1660.87	1664.38	1659.36	1663.33	1658.49	1665.17	1661.93	T	4.23
	L _{1/2}	2128.17	2131.17	2129.40	2130.67	2125.33	2126.63	2128.56	L	2.99
	L ₁	2265.13	2272.00	2264.60	2270.00	2260.60	2262.73	2265.84	T X L	NS
	Mean	2018.06	2022.52	2017.79	2021.33	2014.81	2018.18			
30th day	L ₀	1664.73	1670.33	1661.65	1667.00	1660.82	1664.17	1664.78	T	3.03
	L _{1/2}	2123.00	2125.33	2122.50	2124.00	2119.93	2122.97	2122.96	L	2.14
	L ₁	2259.00	2270.47	2260.00	2266.00	2259.00	2265.93	2263.40	T X L	NS
	Mean	2015.58	2022.04	2014.72	2019.00	2013.25	2017.69			
60th day	L ₀	1654.73	1658.63	1649.47	1653.17	1647.67	1651.20	1652.48	T	NS
	L _{1/2}	2116.64	2118.92	2115.14	2114.57	2113.30	2115.33	2115.65	L	4.34
	L ₁	2273.20	2282.00	2273.20	2287.00	2271.00	2281.50	2277.98	T X L	NS
	Mean	2014.86	2019.85	2012.60	2018.25	2010.66	2016.01			
90th day	L ₀	1660.00	1663.00	1657.85	1660.00	1653.00	1655.93	1658.30	T	3.53
	L _{1/2}	2118.29	2124.29	2116.60	2121.96	2115.78	2120.83	2119.63	L	2.49
	L ₁	2260.77	2266.47	2258.67	2266.33	2255.93	2267.00	2262.53	T X L	NS
	Mean	2013.02	2017.92	2011.04	2016.10	2008.24	2014.59			

[Where, L₀, L_{1/2}, L₁ indicate unlimed, half limed soil, full limed soil respectively, T₀, T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄, T₅ indicate no fertilizer, K @ 30 mg kg^{-1} as MOP, N @ 30 mg kg^{-1} as urea, K @ 30 mg kg^{-1} as MOP and N @ 30 mg kg^{-1} as urea, N @ 60 mg kg^{-1} as urea, K @ 30 mg kg^{-1} MOP and N @ 60 mg kg^{-1} as urea respectively, NS = not significant]

Fig. 3. Effect of liming on the changes of the mean value of different treatments on non-exchangeable K.

exchangeable form of K was converted into non-exchangeable form in limed soil. Increase in non-exchangeable K by liming is mainly due to the transformation of lattice K in soil. Results suggested a dynamic equilibrium among different forms of K in soil. Application of K fertilizer along with N fertilizer significantly increased water soluble

K and decreased non-exchangeable K. Liming of acid soil with half of its requirement and combined application of N and K fertilizers significantly reduced K fixation and increased water soluble K which can easily be taken up by the growing plants.

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